

Alzheimer's disease – A Overview with Dementia and Pathophysiology, Causes, Diagnosis& Treatment

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Abstract:-

Alzheimer's disease is the most common cause of dementia — a gradual decline in memory, thinking, behavior and social skills. These changes affect a person's ability to function. Alzheimer's disease (AD) is increasing at an alarming pace as the population of the United States and the world age. The goal of this review is to describe the current AD drug development pipeline; note trends in clinical trial design, clinical outcome measures, and biomarker use in trials; and review which drug mechanisms of action (MoAs) and biological targets are being pursued. There are currently 187 trials assessing 141 drugs for the treatment of Alzheimer's disease (AD)^[1]. AD is considered a multifactorial disease: two main hypotheses were proposed as a cause for AD, cholinergic and amyloid hypotheses. Unfortunately, there is no cure for Alzheimer's disease, which makes it an even bigger challenge for individuals and caregivers. Alzheimer disease is the most common form of dementia and may contribute to 60–70% of cases, says the global health body ^[2]. The Alzheimer's Association recently released its 2023 Alzheimer's disease Facts and Figures report providing an in-depth look at the latest statistics on Alzheimer's disease. Animal models of AD have been useful in understanding the disease process and in investigating the effects of compounds on pathology and behavior. APP/PS1 mice develop amyloid plaques and show memory impairment ^[3].

Keywords:- Introduction , Pathophysiology, Etiology, Stages of Alzheimer's Disease , Causes

1. Introduction:- Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a progressive neurodegenerative disease. It is characterized by progressive cognitive deterioration together with declining activities of daily living and behavioral changes ^[3]. The disease is named after Dr. Alois Alzheimer. In 1906, Dr. Alzheimer noticed changes in the brain tissue of a woman who had died of an unusual mental illness. Her symptoms included memory loss, language problems, and unpredictable behavior. After she died, he examined her brain and found many abnormal clumps (now called amyloid plaques) and tangled bundles of fibers (now called neurofibrillary, or tau, tangles). Approximately 200,000 people younger than 65 years with AD comprise the

younger onset AD population; 5 million are age 65 years or older^[4]. It is expected that by

Normal Aging	Dementia
Not being able to remember small details of a conversation or event that took place a year ago	Not being able to recall details of recent events or conversations
Not being able to remember the name of an acquaintance	Not recognizing or knowing the names of family members
Forgetting things and events occasionally	Forgetting things or events more frequently
Occasionally have difficulty finding words	Frequent pauses and substitutions when finding words

2050, one new case of AD is expected to develop every 33 seconds, or nearly a million new cases per year, and the total estimated prevalence is expected to be 13.8 Millions. It causes functional as well as structural disturbance of brain's nerve cells. In early means of disease^[5], it also causes synaptic dysfunction of nerve cells thereby affecting the communication within neural circuits which is important for memory and other cognitive functions. AD remains a clinical diagnosis, although cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) and positron emission tomography (PET) biomarkers can increase diagnostic accuracy. Current treatments, including cholinesterase inhibitors and meantime^[6], improve quality of life but do not modify or slow the disease course. Patients who meet typical disease characteristics, excluding other causes such as vascular and fronto-temporal dementias, have a probable diagnosis of AD.

1.1 Normal Aging: - Normal aging is a natural process, while Alzheimer's is a form of dementia, a degenerative condition that gets worse over time. Normal aging and Alzheimer's are very different; however, both involve changes in the brain^[7]. It is necessary to describe what happens in normal ageing and understanding what can go wrong and gives rise to abnormal

conditions such as dementia. Ageing can be distinguished in terms of biological, social and psychological. **Approximately 40% of people over the age of 65 experience some form of memory loss. When there is no underlying medical condition causing this impairment, it is known as “Age-Associated Memory Impairment”, which is considered a part of the normal aging Proces**^[8].

Pathophysiology :- The two pathologic hallmarks of Alzheimer disease are:-

Extracellular beta-amyloid deposits (in neuritic plaques)

Intracellular neurofibrillary tangles (paired helical filaments)

The mechanism by which beta-amyloid peptide and neurofibrillary tangles cause such damage is incompletely understood. There are several theories.

1.2 Extracellular Beta – Amyloid Deposits (in neuritic plaques) :- Beta-amyloid peptide is derived from a transmembrane protein known as an amyloid precursor protein (APP). The beta-amyloid peptide is cleaved from APP by the action of proteases named alpha, beta, and gamma-secretase^[9]. Usually, APP is cleaved by either alpha or beta-secretase and the tiny fragments formed by them are not toxic to neurons. However, sequential cleavage by beta and then gamma-secretase results in 42 amino acid peptides (beta-amyloid 42). Elevation in levels of beta-amyloid 42 leads to aggregation of amyloid that causes neuronal toxicity^[10]. Beta-amyloid 42 favors the formation of aggregated fibrillary amyloid protein over normal APP degradation. APP gene is located on chromosome 21, one of the regions linked to familial Alzheimer's disease. The imbalance between β -amyloid ($A\beta$) production and clearance leads to various types of toxic oligomeric, namely protofibrils, fibrils and plaques depending upon the extent of oligomerization. Plaques are spherical microscopic lesions that have a core of extracellular amyloid beta-peptide surrounded by enlarged axonal endings.

1.3 Intracellular neurofibrillary tangles (paired helical filaments) :- Neurofibrillary tangles (NFTs) are aggregates of hyperphosphorylated tau protein that are most commonly known as a primary biomarker of Alzheimer's disease. Their presence is also found in numerous other diseases known as tauopathies. Neurofibrillary tangles and senile Plaques are dense, mostly insoluble deposits of protein and cellular material outside and around the neurons. Plaques are made of beta-amyloid (Ab), a protein fragment snipped from a larger protein called amyloid precursor protein (APP). These fragments clump together and are mixed with other molecules, neurons, and non-nerve cells^[11].

2. Stages of Alzheimer’s Disease:- 7 Stages of Alzheimer's Disease

Stage 1: Normal Outward Behavior.

Stage 2: Very Mild Changes.

Stage 3: Mild Decline.

Stage 4: Moderate Decline.

Stage 5: Moderately Severe Decline.

Stage 6: Severe Decline.

Stage 7: Very Severe Decline.

Stage 1: - Normal Outward Behavior :- At any age, persons may be free of objective or subjective symptoms of cognitive and functional decline, as well as of associated behavioral and mood changes. We call these mentally healthy persons at any age, stage 1, or normal ^[12].

Stage 2: - Very Mild Changes:- At this stage, subtle symptoms of Alzheimer's don't interfere with their ability to work or live independently. Alzheimer's disease mainly affects older adults over the age of 65. At this age, it's common to have slight functional difficulties they placed something. For example, a person may forget familiar words, a family member's name, or where they placed something ^[13].

Stage 3: - Mild Decline:- The symptoms of Alzheimer's are less clear during stage 3. The most common early symptom is forgetting newly learned information, especially recent events, places and names ^[14].

- Remembering a name
- Recalling recent events
- Remembering where he or she put a valuable object
- Making plans
- Staying organized
- Managing

Stage 4: - Moderate Decline:- This is typically the longest stage, usually lasting many years. During the moderate dementia stage of Alzheimer's disease, people grow more confused and forgetful. They begin to need more help with daily activities and self-care ^[15]. People in the moderate stage of Alzheimer's often require care and assistance.

People in this stage may:

Show increasingly poor judgment and deepening confusion. Individuals lose track of where they are, the day of the week or the season. ...

Experience even greater memory loss. ...

Need help with some daily activities. ...

Undergo significant changes in personality and behavior.

Stage 5: - Moderately Severe Decline:- They may still say words or phrases, but communicating pain becomes difficult. As memory and cognitive skills worsen, significant personality changes may occur and extensive help with daily activities may be required. At this stage, individuals may ^[16]:

Need round-the-clock assistance with daily activities and personal care.

Lose awareness of recent experiences as well as of their surroundings.

Experience changes in physical abilities, including the ability to walk, sit and, eventually, swallow.

Have greater difficulty communicating.

Become increasingly vulnerable to infections, especially pneumonia.

Stage 6: - Severe Decline :- In the stage of AD, plaques and tangles are widespread throughout the brain, and areas of the brain have atrophied further. Patients cannot recognize family and loved ones or communicate in any way. They are completely dependent on others for care. All sense of self seems to vanish. Other symptoms can include:

- Weight loss
- Seizures, skin infections, difficulty swallowing
- Groaning, moaning, or grunting
- Increased sleeping
- Lack of bladder and bowel control

Stage 7:- Very Severe Decline :-

Many basic abilities in a person with Alzheimer's, such as eating, walking, and sitting up, fade during this period. You can stay involved by feeding your loved one with soft, easy-to-swallow food, helping them use a spoon, and making sure they drink.

3. Etiology:-

Alzheimer's disease is a gradual and progressive neurodegenerative disease caused by neuronal cell death. It typically starts in the entorhinal cortex in the hippocampus. There is a genetic role identified for both early and late-onset Alzheimer's disease. Trisomy 21 is a risk factor for early-onset dementia. Several risk factors have been associated with Alzheimer's disease. Increasing age is the most important risk factor for Alzheimer's disease. Traumatic head injury, depression, *cardiovascular* and cerebrovascular disease, higher parental age, smoking, family history of dementia, increased homocysteine levels and presence of APOE e4 allele are known to increase the risk of Alzheimer's disease. Higher education, use of estrogen by women, use of anti-inflammatory agents, leisure activities like reading or playing musical instruments ^[17], healthy diet and regular aerobic exercise is known to decrease the risk of Alzheimer's disease. Having a first-degree relative with Alzheimer's disease increases the risk of developing Alzheimer's disease by 10% to 30%. Individuals with 2 or more siblings with late-onset Alzheimer disease increase their risk of getting Alzheimer's disease by 3-fold as compared to the general population.

3.1 Etiology Factor Alzheimer disease :-

Cardiovascular Disease:- Hypertension, Head Trauma, diabetes.

Environmental Factor:- Tobacco, Smoke, Pesticide.

Metals :- Arsenic, Lead, Copper, Mercury.

Aging :- Free Radical Generation.

Genetics:- Mutation In AAP,PSEN-1, PSEN -2.

3.2 Symptoms & Causes:- The symptoms of Alzheimer's disease progress slowly over several years. Sometimes these symptoms are confused with other conditions and may initially be put down to old age. Symptoms Often Include ^[18]: -

- Inability To Communicate
- Weight loss
- Groaning, Moaning And Grunting
- Increase Sleeping
- No Awareness

3.3 Physical Decline:-

- Dental Skin And Foot Problem.
- Difficulty Swallowing
- Loss Of Bowel And. Bladder Control

4. Causes:-

The exact causes of Alzheimer's disease aren't fully understood. But at a basic level, brain proteins fail to function as usual. This disrupts the work of brain cells, also called neurons, and triggers a series of events. The neurons become damaged and lose connections to each other. They eventually die.

Scientists believe that for most people, Alzheimer's disease is caused by a combination of genetic, lifestyle and environmental factors that affect the brain over time. In less than 1% of

cases, Alzheimer's is caused by specific genetic changes that almost guarantee a person will develop the disease. In these cases, the disease usually begins in middle age.

Researchers trying to understand the cause of Alzheimer's disease are focused on the role of two proteins

4.1 Plaques Beta-amyloid is a fragment of a larger protein. Plaques form when protein pieces called **beta-amyloid** (BAY-tuh AM-uh-loyd) clump together. Beta-amyloid comes from a larger protein found in the fatty membrane surrounding nerve cells. Beta-amyloid is chemically "sticky" and gradually builds up into **plaques**. The most damaging form of beta-amyloid may be **groups of a few pieces** rather than the plaques themselves. The small clumps may block cell-to-cell signaling at synapses.

4.2 Tangles: - Tangles destroy a vital cell transport system made of proteins. This electron microscope picture shows a cell with some healthy areas and other areas where tangles are forming. Tangles form when tau is misfiled in a very specific way. In Alzheimer's disease, the tau forms a C-shape in the core of the tangle with a loose end sticking out randomly. Tangles form inside of neurons and interfere with the cellular machinery used to create and recycle proteins, which ultimately kills the cell ^[18].

4.3 Diagnosis & Treatment:- Healthcare providers use several methods to determine if a person with memory issues has Alzheimer's disease. The National Institute of Neurologic and Communicative Disorders and Stroke and Alzheimer Disease and Related Disorders Association has set criteria for the diagnosis of AD. Unfortunately, there is no single test that can confirm Alzheimer's disease. This involves a careful medical evaluation, including a thorough medical history, mental status testing, a physical and neurological exam, blood tests and brain imaging exams, including: -

- Neurological Test
- Blood Test
- Brain imaging Test
- Neuropsychological Test

4.4 Neuropsychological Test: Neuropsychological testing refers to a number of tests that healthcare providers use to get information about how your brain works. Specially trained psychologists look at the results to better understand the relationship between your brain health and behavior, and mood and thinking (cognition). You may be given different types of test, including^[19]:

Memory test: Repeat a list of words, sentences, or numbers.

Cognition test: Explain how two items are like. For instance, if you see a picture of a dog and a cat, you might answer that they're both animals or that they are both pets.

4.5 Verbal communication test: Name some items as the person giving the test points at them. You might also be given a letter of the alphabet and told to list words that start with that letter.

4.6 Motor tests: These might include tasks such as inserting pegs into a pegboard using one hand and then the other.

You might also be given tests to see how your hearing and vision affect your thinking and memory.

4.8 Brain imaging Test :- Imaging tests can be used to visualize the structure of the brain, skull, or blood vessels. Some diagnostic tests also provide information about activity in different regions of the brain. Interventional procedures for treatment of brain conditions are often done with real time imaging guidance as well.

5. Discussion:-

The fight against Alzheimer's disease is gaining momentum, fuelled by groundbreaking research and promising advancements. While there's no cure yet, new discoveries are paving the way for better treatment and prevention strategies. Let's dive into some of the most exciting developments:

It's important to stay informed about the latest developments and consult with healthcare professionals for personalized advice regarding risk reduction and potential treatment options. Together, we can continue to push the boundaries of Alzheimer's research and create a brighter future for those affected by this disease ^[20].

6. Conclusion:-

Ultimately, the conclusion of Alzheimer's disease is a loss of function and independence. While there is no cure, there are treatments available to manage symptoms and improve quality of life for individuals and their families. Here are some additional points to remember about the conclusion of Alzheimer's disease:

The rate of progression varies greatly from person to person. Some individuals may live with the disease for many years, while others may decline more rapidly. There is no single cause of Alzheimer's disease, and it is likely a combination of genetic, environmental, and lifestyle

factors. Research is ongoing, and there is hope for future treatments that may slow or even stop the progression of the disease. If you have any further questions or concerns about Alzheimer's disease, please reach out to a healthcare professional. there's no definitive conclusion to Alzheimer's disease, as it's a progressive and ultimately fatal neurodegenerative condition. However, its progression can be characterized by several stages, with the final stage leading to complete dependence on others for even basic needs ^[21].

Research into Alzheimer's disease is ongoing, and there's hope that new treatments or even a cure may be found in the future. However, the conclusion for individuals living with the disease is currently one of managing symptoms and providing supportive care.

It's important to remember that Alzheimer's disease affects people differently, and the progression of the disease can vary. Some individuals may live for many years with the disease, while others may progress more quickly.

If you or someone you know is living with Alzheimer's disease, there are many resources available to provide support and information. The Alzheimer's Association is a great starting point.

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